

ABSTRACT

Analysis of cosmopolitanism and characterization of MAGs (Metagenome-Assembled Genomes) from environments at the São Paulo Zoo

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The MAGs (Metagenome-Assembled Genomes) have become important objects of study to understand microbial communities in diverse environments. According to Setubal (2021), MAGs can be classified in two ways: a) Species MAG (SMAG): a MAG classified at species level and for which there is at least one isolate genome as reference; b) Hypothetical MAG (HMAG): a classified MAG at less specific taxonomic levels and without a deposited isolate genome. The HMAGs, if there is another sufficiently similar genome from a study in a different geographic location, may still be classified under Hypothetical MAG Preserved (CHMAG). Faced with the growing number of genomes available in public data bases, as well as the publication of MAG catalogs, in this work we aim to characterize SMAGs and CHMAGs recovered from three different Zoo environments from São Paulo (compost, howler monkey feces and reservoir water), comparing them to orthologous genomes. We initially classify our MAGs as SMAGs then, using Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) as a metric (ANI \geq 95%), our SMAGs were compared with genomes deposited in GenBank and JGI, and with the Genomes from Earth's Microbiomes (Nayfach, 2021) and Non-Human catalogs Primates Gut Microbiome (Manara, 2019) and we consider orthologous genomes those genome pairs for which ANI \geq 95%. The same methodology was followed to HMAGs for this we were able to determine 34 are CHMAGs. Many orthologous genomes found for MAGs in howler monkey feces are from the human digestive system, while others were recovered from the intestinal microbiota of monkeys from Old World and New world. For water reservoir MAGs, all orthologous genomes come from of freshwater samples, except ZLKR40 which has an ortholog recovered from a saline aquatic environment. We compare orthologous genomes in a set to each other using the MAGset tool, which uses the concept of Genomic Region of Interest (region of at least 5,000 bp) with differential presence between a target genome and one or more orthologous reference genomes. GRIs existing only in target SMAGs were analyzed to find genes that could indicate adaptations to their environment. As example of this analysis, we found in ZC4RG04 a gene in positive RGI (exclusive of our genome) that encodes a protein from the GH3 CAZyme family that plays a series of functions, including the degradation of cellulosic biomass. degradation.

Keywords: Metagenome; Composting; Howler Monkeys; Reservoir Water.

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